

IMPROVEMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL TRAINING OF FUTURE EDUCATORS BASED ON AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH

Jabborova Marifat Kodiraliyeva

Teacher at the department of Social and Humanitarian Sciences, Fergana State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8193377>

Abstract. *An educator performs an important, proud and at the same time responsible task of raising the young generation to become worthy children of our nation. The political maturity of an educator helps him to understand his responsibility to the people and society for the quality of children's education, his creative approach to solving educational tasks, constantly improving his skills and helping his colleagues grow.*

Keywords: *skill, integrative approach, socio-political, pedagogical skill, principle, teamwork, political level, safe environment.*

Introduction. The rapid development of science and technology poses huge challenges to modern pedagogues. On the basis of an integrative approach, in order to improve the pedagogical training of future teachers, to arouse their strong and stable interest in the profession, to ensure that they have practical work and pedagogical understanding of the educational system is one of the important tasks ahead. A person who has great desire and enthusiasm for the profession of education, that is, to be a real mentor in the education and upbringing of a healthy generation, who quickly and deeply understands the demands of the times, who is consistent in his scientific, social and political level, and pedagogical skills. A person who loves children, a true patriot and a hard worker can achieve it.

An educator performs an important, proud and at the same time responsible task of raising the young generation to become worthy children of our nation. The political maturity of an educator helps him to understand his responsibility to the people and society for the quality of children's education, his creative approach to solving educational tasks, constantly improving his skills and helping his colleagues grow.

Therefore, the educator should first of all be educated, know the life of the country where he lives, understand the laws of nature and society, be socially active, know the pedagogy of general and pre-school education, the psychology and physiology of children, and the characteristics of young children. Also, the teacher's approach to the analysis of pedagogical phenomena from a scientific point of view makes it possible to realize the success of comprehensive development of children.

As a facilitator, the future teacher uses his knowledge, skills and resources to educate and educate children. The educator plans the process of education and upbringing, creates a developmental environment that contributes to the comprehensive development of the child and unlocks his potential. For this purpose, the future teacher should know the characteristics of the child's development, understand his feelings, and be able to determine the needs and interests of each child. The educator creates such an environment in the group where every child should feel smart, capable and involved in the educational process. The educator contributes to the development of the child's ability to act independently, to achieve results and achieve achievements, and to enjoy them. A teacher also helps children feel confident that each child can

get help and encouragement from them when they need it. The teacher documents, analyzes and evaluates his professional activity in order to constantly improve his professional competence.

During his pedagogical activity, the educator respects the opinion and experience of the child's parents and representatives of the local community, and builds his activities on the basis of consensus with them, relying on his pedagogical skills.

Pedagogical skill is not an innate talent or a characteristic passed from generation to generation, but a product of research and creative work.

The success of educational activities in improving the pedagogical training of future educators based on an integrative approach depends on the presence of pedagogical skills. Pedagogical skills are the basis for achieving pedagogical skills.

So, pedagogy is the art of constantly improving the education of the young generation at a high level.

In order to improve the pedagogical training of future educators based on an integrative approach, the future educator should first know the methodological foundations of preschool pedagogy, the laws and factors of personality development, and tasks. When it comes to educating the young generation, this very complex and multifaceted task can be performed only by a qualified teacher with pedagogical skills.

Pedagogical skill means work on oneself, creative work. The effectiveness of the educational process depends primarily on the teacher's scientific potential, reputation in front of children, personal qualities, scientific talent, skills, and friendly relations with children.

Pedagogical skill consists of several elements: humanism of the pedagogue (orientation to humanity), knowledge of specialization, pedagogical ability, pedagogical technique.

Devotion to the teaching profession; full mastery of personal and professional qualities of a pedagogue; the pedagogue's mental and psychological preparation; The pedagogue's special and specialized scientific and theoretical knowledge and skills are the components that form the basis of training for educational activities.

Pedagogical skill is a set of personal qualities of a pedagogue, scientific and technical, pedagogical knowledge and professional skills and abilities.

The effectiveness of pedagogical skill also depends on the level of pedagogical ability of the teacher.

Pedagogical ability appears and develops in the process of activity. Pedagogical ability has the following types: knowledge ability, ability to explain, ability to observe, ability to speak, ability to communicate.

Pedagogical abilities and skills are not easily formed in the educator. In order to achieve his goal, a person who has chosen this profession must continuously study, learn and search, work creatively, quickly understand reality and deeply feel how necessary his work is for society.

Every future teacher pedagogue should know well the principles of organizing the educational process in the preschool educational organization and organize the educational process based on it.

Results: The principles determine the results expected from preschool educational organizations, the characteristics of the developmental environment that must be provided by the pedagogues of preschool educational organizations in the implementation of the state curriculum, and integrative approaches to the education and development of preschool children.

Discussion. It is necessary for future educators to know the principles of the educational and educational process of the preschool educational organization and to follow these principles in their pedagogical activities. These principles include:

- Recognition of childhood as a special value. Childhood is an important age and life period. Childhood is characterized by the ability of children to learn and change more than adults as a result of their educational experiences. Childhood is an important stage of child development, when the right to a happy childhood is recognized.

- Taking into account the child's rights, individuality and development opportunities. All children are born with great potential and each has an innate talent. Every child is unique. All children have the right to protect and promote their health and well-being, as well as equal access to quality preschool education.

- Children, including children with special needs, are recognized as active participants in the educational process and contribute to their learning and development by choosing the type of activity, participating in planning, satisfying their natural interest in knowledge.

Preschool education is a harmonious process of care, education and upbringing; it ensures the formation of the child in all areas of development; this determines the interdependence of all areas of development in the process of education and training, as well as the need to provide various and comprehensive opportunities for education and integration in each area of development.

- Maintaining, strengthening and providing a safe environment for the child's health. Meeting various needs of the child, including the need for movement; through active games and daily physical exercises, children develop their feelings, large and small motor skills; they explore the environment in motion and manage various objects; they can distinguish the effects and possibilities of their body, they start to take care of it and adopt a healthy lifestyle.

- Learning and development through play. Play is an important approach to teaching preschool children. The game brings joy and motivates children, allows them to learn new skills and knowledge, learn about themselves and the world around them. Pre-school education recognizes the child's right to play, the importance of play for the child and its pedagogical potential in promoting individual development, learning and well-being.

Cooperation of preschool education organization with family, neighborhood, school. The well-being of the child depends on the understanding of the importance of the organization of preschool education by his family members and relatives. Children learn and develop better when parents and the local community are involved and involved in the learning process.

Recognition of national, historical and cultural traditions, spiritual wealth and respect for the culture of other nations, children's desire to learn their own national culture, language, and traditions when they are recognized with respect and interest will increase. Supporting the development of a child in a preschool education organization is a team effort, and the director of the preschool education organization is responsible for its implementation.

These principles form the basis of the process of education and upbringing in the preschool education organization, and are a guide for pedagogues in planning and implementing the state curriculum, making pedagogical and practical decisions on the education and development of each child.

Conclusion: The skill of an educator is that he knows when to support timid children, and when to teach empathy to an aggressive one. He should notice the child's abilities and not only

support him, but also convince the parents of the need to develop the child's abilities. The educator cannot achieve this without observation, good memory and tact.

REFERENCES

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2017 yil 30 sentyabrdagi "O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha ta'lim vazirligi faoliyatini tashkil etish to'g'risida"gi PQ-3305-son Qarori.
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2017 yil 7 fevraldagi «O'zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo'yicha Xarakterlar Strategiyasi to'g'risida»gi PF-4947-son Farmoni. O'zbekiston Respublikasi qonun hujjatlari to'plami. 2017 yil. 6-son 70 – modda.
3. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2016 yil 29 dekabrda qabul qilingan «2017-2021 yillarda Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimini yanada takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida»gi PQ 2707 sonli qarori.
4. Jabborova M.Q. Bo'lajak pedagoglarni tayyorlash tizimida malakaviy amaliyotning rol. Scientific progress volume 3 | issue 4 | 2022 issn: 2181-160
5. Jabborova M.Q. Tarbiyachi kasbining ma'naviy axloqiy negizlari. "Yangi o'zbekistonning umidli yos central asian research journal for interdisciplinary studies (carjis) ilmiy jurnali bilan hamkorlikda. Yangi o'zbekistonning umidli yoshlarilari" 1(1)- son 03.28.22.son.
6. Jabborova M.Q. Jamiyat ijtimoiy taraqqiyotida innovatsion texnologiyalarning ahamiyati. "Экономика и социум" №6(85) ч.1 2021
7. Jabborova M.Q. Maxmutaliyeva Z. Tarbiyachi nutqiga qo'yiladigan pedagogik talablar. Uacademia ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali научно-методический журнал scientific-methodical journal issn (e) – 2181 – 1334 barcha sohalar bo'yicha vol 3, issue 7 (27), february 2022 part – 2.
8. Jabborova M.Q. A.Soliyev. Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari tarbiyalanuvchilari ongida milliy musiqiy ohanglarga moyillikni shakllantirishda milly cholg'ularning o'rni. Science and innovation xalqaro ilmiy jurnali 2022 yil 1-son.
9. Jabborova M.Q, Sharipova G. Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari va ko'p tarmoqli ixtisoslashtirilgan maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida turli yoshdagi bolalarni grammatik nutqini shakllantirish. "Research Focus" academy of sciences and innovations international scientific journal research focus volume 1 issue 3. Research focus xalqaro ilmiy jurnali 2022 yil 3-son.